

THE IMPACT OF INDUSTRY NOVEL IN CHARLOTTE BRONTE WORKS

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Abstract. *The article focuses on the impact of industry novel in Charlotte Bronte works. Victorian era considered as workshop of the world. Industry well developed in this period. Industry influenced not only people's life but in literature also. Writers of Victorian era tried to show power of industry in their novels.*

Key words: *victorian period, industry, impact, novel, character, factory.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается влияние индустриального романа на творчество Шарлотты Бронте. Викторианская эпоха считается мастерской мира. Промышленность в этот период хорошо развита. Промышленность влияла не только на жизнь людей, но и на литературу. Писатели викторианской эпохи пытались показать в своих романах мощь промышленности.*

Ключевые слова: *викторианский период, промышленность, влияние, роман, персонаж, фабрика.*

Victorian age plays an important role in English literature. We can see three main stages of Victorian period. These stages created social novel in English literature.

Addressing the socio-historical topic, the Charlotte Bronte turned to the country's history. Charlotte Bronte is well known writer of Victorian age. She writes over six novels during her life time. One of them is “Shirley”. "Shirley" covers the issue between factory and factory owners and workers against the backdrop of a social problem. Charlotte, who was a supporter of truth, sided with those who fought for justice. Charlotte Bronte, like E. Gaskell, who strongly denounced the unequal distribution of labor and treated the workers lightly, witnessed the hardships of thousands of middle-class people. Novels about such an industry show that there is a typological commonality in the works of both writers. The story of the play begins with the arrival of a large nobleman, Robert Moore, in a small town. He rents a factory owned by the Kildare family for the production of fabric. He focuses on the redevelopment and development of the factory. The introduction of new machinery into the factory results in layoffs, and workers attempt to break the machinery. Caroline, a distant cousin of Mr. Moore, comes to town and witnesses the plight of the workers. He advises Robert to improve his relations with the workers and that the labor force in the factory should be distributed equally. But Mr. Moore ignores this and decides to sue the workers who broke the machines. Robert Moore, who carefully watched his workers, finds out who caused it and arrests him to the police. Such scenes described in the work are similar to the events in "North and South" by E. Gaskell. In "North and South" Margaret Hale, the heroine of the work, witnesses the life of workers, just like Caroline. However, in North and South, Mr. Thornton, the factory owner, does not arrest the police even though his workers riot. This is where the difference between Robert Moore and Mr. Thornton becomes apparent. Robert gets into a heated argument with Caroline's uncle, Mr. Halstone, over a problem at the factory. After the death

of her parents, Caroline was placed under the care of her uncle, and at her uncle's insistence, she could not see Robert for a long time. He often talked with Robert about the workers' problem, and a friendship developed between them. But now the uncle himself starts to prevent it. Shirley Kildare, one of the main characters of the play, appears on these events. Shirley talks to Mr. Halstone about Robert Moore renting the factory. But Mr. Helstone has a harsh opinion about the young manufacturer. Now the action of the two girls, Caroline and Shirley Kildare, who use Robert Moore in the center of the work, begins to appear. Robert Moore considered Caroline worthy of him and Shirley as his business partner. Robert faces a Luddite rebellion and Shirley comes to his aid. In the image of Shirley Kildar, one of the heroes of the work, we can see the actions of a business girl on the one hand, and on the other hand, we can see the image of her selfless patron who established a fund to help the poor. Shirley Kildare is a determined girl who was educated by governesses, i.e. teachers, in a wealthy family. He belongs to the group of those who think about every step and can speak their opinion boldly. Even his pride can be seen in some events. Opposite her, Caroline Halstone is intelligent but often stumbles due to her lack of self-confidence. He can be a good friend to Robert. Some aspects of Shirley are similar to Margaret Hale in North and South. Margaret, like Shirley, advocates peaceful resolution of the problem between workers and employers. Margaret and Shirley have the idea that the needs of both parties should be taken into account in this solution. Just as Shirley encouraged Robert Moore to compromise with the workers, so Margaret offers Mr. Thornton the same. The events described in the play are further complicated by the fact that the fabric designed by Mr. Moore does not sell. Shirley Kildare solves the problem. The writer, who has moved away from romantic feelings, is now able to show the social problem as well as its solution. In the character of Shirley Kildare, she once again reveals the courage of a girl from an aristocratic family, not the middle class. In contrast to the character of Margaret created by Elizabeth Gaskell, Shirley's business sense is visible. Margaret does not have this trait. But Margaret is as good an observer as Shirley. Both Margaret and Shirley want both parties to not suffer. This is the aspect that makes them general. The Victorian ideal of a home angel leaves his home and seeks a solution to a social problem in his literary work. The author tries to show the consequences of unemployment on the national scale based on real events. Avoiding autobiographical details, the work realistically describes the problem that arose in the industrial development of the astute observer Charlotte Bronte. In "Shirley", which is completely different from other works, the main character appears in the middle of the play, not at the beginning. The work is narrated by the third character, not from the language of the first character. The appearance of a hero who can provide an important solution to the development of events in the middle of the work also causes unexpected objections from critics. The English critic Elliot Miriam points out that Charlotte Bronte, who used an unusual narrative style in "Shirley", opened a new side [1]. Judith Mitchell considers it the weakest work among Bronte's works[2]. Regarding the historical facts described in the work, Linda Hunt says that the realistic events in the work are true, but there are flaws in the characters of the work[3]. Critic Peter Garrett points out that the story of the work is built in an unusual way, that the events are not followed around a single solution. In his opinion, the events narrated in the work come from different sides and connect in one line. The characters of the work also try to justify their actions along this line. [4] A new image of Charlotte Bronte is revealed in the one-sided opinions of the critics. The author, who switched to a completely new story, looks at the history of the country and tries to express the problem in a realistic way. Even the romantic nature of a woman seems to have disappeared. Carolina Halstone and Shirley Keldar,

who are depicted in the picture, are similar to people who are not immune to these sensitive feelings. Their romantic nature is also not visible. Caroline Halstone is smart, as we've mentioned, but she doesn't have the courage to talk openly with Robert Moore. Even in giving advice to Robert, his hesitation can be seen. Growing up under the influence of her uncle, Caroline is forced to obey her uncle Mr. Halstone's orders without question. It reminds of the typical look of a true submissive Victorian Englishwoman. Shirley Keldar is a member of the aristocratic class. Robert Moore tries to find a solution to the events around him. Shirley, observing the mood of protest of the workers, felt a feeling of pity for them in her heart. The aristocratic girl's pitying view of the workers is a rare find, not found in any of Charlotte Bronte's other works. Shirley, educated by teachers, plays an important role in the happy ending of the work, as noted by critics S. M. Gilbert and S. Gubar. [5] It is observed that the author paid special attention to Shirley in finding such a solution of the work.

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